

which results in a total of two round-trip requests for a single multidrop.

The proposed consensus involves the following steps:

1. The leader constructs a new block and broadcasts the block header to all validators. Meanwhile, the leader broadcasts the contents of the block with the coding to the eraser. This is called the "announcement" phase.

2. The validators check the validity of the block header, sign the block header with the BLS signature and send the signature back to the leader.

3. The leader waits for at least $2ff + 1$ valid signatures from the validators (including the leader's own signatures) and aggregates them into a BLS multi-signature. The leader then broadcasts the aggregated multi-signature along with a bitmap of the changes the validators have signed. Together with step 3, the 'preparation' phase of the PBFT is completed.

4. The validators check if the multi-signature has at least $2ff + 1$ valid signatures, check the block content transactions broadcast from the leader in step 1, sign the received message from step 3 and send it back to the leader.

5. The leader waits for at least $2ff + 1$ valid signatures and from step 4, combines them together into a BLS multi-signature and creates bitmaps, registers all those who signed. The leader then captures the new block with all signatures, multi-signatures and bitmaps and transmits the new block to all validators. Together with step 5, the PBFT 'commit' phase is completed [1; 5].

Consensus validators are elected on a Proof-of-Stake basis. The proposed protocol differs from the existing PBFT in that a validator with more voting shares has more votes than others, rather than one signature one vote. Instead of waiting for at least $2ff + 1$ signatures from validators, the leader waits for signatures from validators who collectively hold at least $2ff + 1$ voting shares.

The traditional procedure of uploading blockchain history and reconstructing the current state is too slow to allow changes to be repeated (it takes several days for the Ethereum blockchain to fully synchronise history), given that the current state is much smaller than the entire blockchain history. Uploading the current state over a time period of an epoch is possible compared to uploading the entire history. In order to optimise the state synchronisation process, it is suggested to make the blockchain state as small as possible.

In Ethereum, many accounts are empty and waste blockchain state space. Empty accounts cannot be deleted due to possible replay errors when old transactions are resubmitted to a deleted account. This problem can be solved by preventing replay attacks by allowing transactions to specify a hash of the current block: the transaction is only valid up to a certain number (e.g. 300) of blocks following the block of the specified hash. In this way, old accounts can be securely deleted, significantly speeding up blockchain state checking [1].

Thus new validators that join the Shard first load the current state of that shard so that they can quickly

start checking transactions. To ensure that the current uploaded state is valid, the new node must do the appropriate validation. Instead of loading the entire blockchain history and replaying all transactions to verify the current state, the new node loads the historical blockchain headers and verifies the headers by verifying their signatures.

As long as there is a cryptographic component (e.g., hash pointers and signatures) from the current state to the genesis block, the state is valid. Verifying signatures is not computationally inexpensive and it takes a significant amount of time to verify all signatures, starting from the genesis block. To mitigate this problem, the first block of each epoch is proposed to include an additional hash pointer to the first block of the last epoch. In this way, the new node can go through the blocks during an epoch when tracing the hash pointers to the genesis block. This will greatly speed up the verification of the current state of the blockchain [5].

The proposed consensus uses an approach that differs from those previously discussed - with Proof of Share (PoS) as a validator registration mechanism or Sybil attack prevention mechanism. In order to become a validator, future participants (or interested parties) must bid on a certain number of tokens to become eligible to participate. The number of tokens pledged determines the number of voting shares intended for the validator. Such a method contains a main chain and a Shardi set. The main chain serves as an identity registry, while the Shardi chains store individual blockchain states and simultaneously process transactions. This algorithm uses randomness generation by combining a random function checker (VRF) and a delay checker (VDF) and includes PoS in the sharding process, which shifts the fragment protection issues from a minimum number of nodes to a minimum number of voting shares [6].

Each voting particle corresponds to one vote in the BFT consensus. Stakers receive voting shares proportional to their tokens. Voting shares are then randomly assigned to the sharding. The tokens become validators for the fragments for which they vote.

Assigning individual voting shares to Shards rather than individual validators. The safety of sharding by voting shares is that even if for all pledged tokens 14 are malicious validators, one validator is assigned to one Shard. In such a case, in the worst case scenario where a single malicious validator holds all the tokens (voting shares), it is less than 13 voting tokens in that Shard. The reason is that the stakes for each Shard are mm times less than the stakes of the whole network, where mm is the number of Shards. Thus preventing attacks by harmful validators instead of sharding by validators, the voting shares are split (one share, entitled to vote, is assigned to one shard).

In this method, the price of a voting share is set algorithmically, so that it is small enough that harmful participants cannot concentrate their voting power in a single Shard. The share price has voting power is set in tokens.

This solution is functional like the minimum number of nodes in a shard described in other PoW-based solutions [1; 7].

This approach is robust to fluctuations in the number of validators. It does not set a lower limit on the number of validators in each fragment, as in other solutions such as Zilliqa. An adaptive PoS-based model is adopted so that attackers can never occupy more than 13 voting shares in a single Shard, which makes it robust.

Developed criteria, indicators and methods to evaluate the performance of the integrated model for the implementation of blockchain technology in the digital environment of the educational process.

References:

1. Technical Whitepaper Harmony Team Version 2. <https://harmony.one/whitepaper.pdf>
2. Alangot B., Suresh M., Raj A. S. Reliable collective cosigning to scale blockchain with strong consistency. Proceedings of the Network and Distributed System Security Symposium (DISS'18), 2018.
3. David K. Gifford, Doctoral Dissertation, Information Storage in a Decentralized Computer System.
4. Kokoris-Kogias E., Jovanovic P., Gailly N., Khoffi I., Gasser L. and B. Ford. Enhancing Bitcoin Security and Performance with Strong Consistency via Collective Signing. In Proceedings of the 25th USENIX Conference on Security Symposium, 2016.
5. Kiayias A., I. Konstantinou, A. Russell, B. David, and R. Oliynykov. Ouroboros: A provably secure proof-of-stake blockchain protocol. Cryptology ePrint Archive, Report 2016/889, 2016. <http://eprint.iacr.org/>
6. Loi Luu, Viswesh Narayanan, Chaodong Zheng, Kunal Baweja, Seth Gilbert, and Prateek Saxena. A secure sharding protocol for open blockchains. In Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, CCS '16, pages 17–30, New York, NY, USA, 2016. ACM.
7. David K. Gifford, Doctoral Dissertation, Information Storage in a Decentralized Computer System.